

Sub micron-quality cleaving of glass with elliptical ultrafast Bessel beams

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The material processing technique of “stealth” nanomachining is based on translating a longitudinally-extended beam such as a Bessel beam into a transparent sample to generate extended nanochannels which leads to subsequent internal stress that facilitates high quality cleaving. In this letter, we compare the quality of such cleaves in glass samples obtained using Bessel beams with both circularly symmetric and elliptical transverse profiles. We find that the use of an elliptical Bessel beam generates elliptical nanochannels that greatly improves the cleavage quality and cut material strength by aligning the centre of the cleavage plane with the centre of the machined channels. These results are interpreted using numerical simulations that show how elliptical nanochannels enhance the intensity and localization of the tensile stress distribution in glass under bending when compared to channels with circular cross-sections.

The high peak power of infrared ultrafast laser pulses results in strongly-localized nonlinear ionization and energy deposition within transparent materials¹. Depending on the deposited energy, a range of material damage can be observed, including index modification², voids³ or cracks⁴. Depending on the energy and focussing parameters, an intense ultrafast pulse can also undergo dynamical filamentation^{5,6}, which can be combined with high-speed scanning to generate a series of sub-micron channels within the bulk of a material which together form a weakened plane allowing the material to cleave⁷. This technique leads to improved cleaved surface quality and edge quality compared to other techniques based on crack formation after illumination by ns or sub-ns pulses^{8,9} or based on V-groove surface ablation¹⁰, because material separation occurs without either material loss or debris.

In this context, the use of “nondiffracting” beams has opened up a number of opportunities in laser processing of transparent materials. Such nondiffracting beams are formed by an interference pattern that produces one or several high intensity spots that maintain their high intensity over an extended propagation distance^{11–13}. These structures are remarkably resistant to nonlinear deformation, provided the interference angle and nonlinear losses are high enough. In this case, the losses in the central intensity lobe are compensated by a flow of energy from the other beam lobes^{14–17}. Perhaps the most well-known of such beams are the family of Bessel beams, which have found important applications in nano-channel formation^{18–23}.

Bessel beams have also been applied to “stealth” material processing⁸ to induce cleavage in transparent dielectrics²⁴. These experiments used picosecond pulses and a circularly symmetric transverse profile but, as we show here, the use of such a symmetric Bessel beam yields a cleavage plane that does not exactly follow the line of machined channels. In this Letter, however, we demonstrate how the use of an elliptical beam profile to generate

elliptical nanochannels greatly improves cleave uniformity by aligning the cleave plane with the channels. Using 3-point bending tests, we quantitatively compare the cleave characteristics obtained using elliptical and circularly symmetric Bessel beams, showing improved cleave quality with elliptical beams. Our results represent a significant advance in the use of elliptical beams for machining applications compared to previous studies that have studied elliptical surface chipping²⁵, and crack formation associated with elliptical damage regions⁹. In addition, our numerical modelling which shows higher stress contrast associated with elliptical channels can also explain recent proof-of-principle cleavage studies using elliptical Bessel beams²⁶.

To begin, we first show experimental results of cleaving in glass using symmetric Bessel beam illumination to highlight the particular problem we aim to address. The experimental setup here is very similar to that described in Meyer *et al.*²⁶, using stretched 2.3 ps pulses from an amplified Ti:Sapphire laser system at central wavelength 800 nm and 5 kHz repetition rate. Stretched pulses in the picosecond regime were previously shown to lead to good cleaveability of samples with stealth nanomachining²⁴. Zeroth order circularly-symmetric Bessel beams were produced by an axicon lens, further demagnified by a telescope arrangement so as to generate a Bessel beam of cone angle 16.5 degrees, Bessel zone length 150 μm (in air), and a central spot diameter of 1.0 μm . Fig. 1(a) shows scanning electron microscopy (SEM) images of a typical cleaved surface obtained using a pulse energy of 18 μJ . Here the borosilicate glass sample (Schott D263M) of thickness 150 μm was translated perpendicularly to the beam so as to generate a line of circular nanochannels of diameter ~ 320 nm and separation 5 μm . The channels extend over the full thickness of the sample. Cleavage was obtained by applying mechanical pressure in a 3 point bending setup (see Fig. 2).

The figure shows clearly how the cleavage plane does not pass through the centers of the machined nanochannels but is rather displaced by ~ 2 μm . Moreover, the

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cleavage does not occur along a line parallel to the centers of the nanochannels but rather it shows random variation. To understand these results and to consider how they can be improved using elliptical nanochannels, we have performed numerical modelling of how the transverse cross-section of the channels impacts the stress distribution observed under bending for (b) circular and (c) elliptical nanochannels. This modelling used SolidWorksTM software with a channel diameter of 360 nm for the circular case and channel dimensions of $720 \times 360 \text{ nm}^2$ for the elliptical case²⁶, and considered a channel depth of 150 nm. The stress was calculated numerically from the (tensor) linear elasticity equation for conditions of static equilibrium with pressure uniformly applied along the centre-line of the sample with both side ends maintained fixed. Note that full modelling over the experimental channel depth of $150 \mu\text{m}$ is computationally prohibitive, but these modelling results at reduced depth clearly show the qualitative difference between the two cases.

FIG. 1. (a) Scanning electron microscope image of cleaved glass sample using $18 \mu\text{J}$ pulse energy with circularly-symmetric Bessel beams. It is clear that the cleaved plane does not pass through the channels (along which cleaving might be expected). Fig. 1(b) and (c) show results from numerical modelling of the stress σ_{xx} induced in a glass slide under bending when it is perforated by: (b) a cylindrically symmetric 360 nm diameter channel and (c) an elliptical channel with major axis 720 nm and minor axis 360 nm. Note that bending is around the y -axis.

The results show the calculated tensile stress tensor component σ_{xx} , for bending around y -axis. For the circularly symmetric channel shown in Fig1(b), it is apparent that the stress is distributed over a wide region, reaching its half-maximum (~ 40 a.u.) more than 200 nm away from the centre where cleaving might intuitively be expected. This observation explains the results in Fig. 1(a) that show how the cleaving is not guided through the center of the circularly-symmetric channels. In contrast, as shown in Fig. 1(c) for an elliptical hole with major axis twice longer as the minor axis, the computed

stress shows: (i) enhancement compared to previous situation by a factor $\sim 30 \%$ and (ii) a maximum stress (~ 100 a.u.) localized at the extremities of the ellipse major axis and half-maximum (~ 50 a.u.) reached closer to the Oy axis (~ 100 nm). These results suggest that the use of elliptical nanochannels should provide a more precisely localised cleavage plane at the channel centres and indeed this is what we see in our experiments. (Note that as we discuss further below, the elliptical Bessel beam used in our experiments actually show two lateral lobes that can generate additional elliptical nanochannels at high input pulse energy ($18 \mu\text{J}$)²⁶. We have also numerically modelled the stress induced by such side channels and no qualitative difference was observed. This is attributed to the fact that side channels are placed at relatively long distance ($\sim 1.7 \mu\text{m}$) from the main central nanochannel.)

We now present results of our experiments where we have performed a detailed comparison between circularly symmetric and elliptical beams applied to cleaving of glass. The experimental laser parameters used were described above. For the generation of Bessel beams with elliptical transverse profile, we use Fourier filtering to remove a specific range of spatial frequencies²⁶. The experimental approach is shown in Fig. 2(a). We first laser-processed the samples by a single pass at constant speed $v = 25 \text{ mm/s}$ at a repetition rate of 5 kHz over the full width of the $20 \times 20 \text{ mm}^2$ samples. The values of speed and pulse duration were chosen because we evaluated them as the best conditions for cleaving glass with symmetric Bessel beams. We wished to retain these parameters when using the elliptical Bessel beam configuration so as to isolate clearly the advantage of the beam ellipticity. In building the setup and choosing experimental parameters, we have ensured that the samples, the translation stage and input Bessel beam with circular polarization were identical for x and y scanning in the plane transverse to the pulse propagation, such that symmetric Bessel beams gave indistinguishable results if the samples were processed along x or y axis. The translation motion was begun before the sample and finished afterwards to avoid any variation in speed over the sample area. The loss of energy due to filtering to produce the elliptical Bessel beam was compensated and the pulse energies indicated below were always measured at the sample site.

Then after laser-processing (Fig. 2(a)), we performed cleaving with three-point bending as represented in Fig. 2(b). The glass sample was bent by a razor blade mounted on a micrometric translation stage. The position of the blade was precisely adjusted under a microscope over the laser-processed line within less than $10 \mu\text{m}$ (Fig. 2(c)). To quantify the ability to cleave or to bend, we recorded the value of the deflection needed to fracture the sample. Fracture may then happen in two ways (cf Fig. 2(e)): (i) cleaving - which means that the sample separates in two pieces following the laser-processed line; or (ii) breaking, which covers all other cases (fracture not following by the laser-processed line, separation into

FIG. 2. Concept of the experiment. (a) Laser writing configurations for elliptical and circularly symmetric Bessel beams. (b) 3-lines bending test. Glass sample is bent by a blade moved by a translation stage with $5 \mu\text{m}$ precision. (c,d) Geometrical configuration of the laser processed line towards the bending axis. (c) First experiment to compare the ability of the beams to induce cleaving. (d) Second experiment to compare the ability for bending of laser-processed samples. (e) Summary on the experimental procedure for processing and sorting the samples.

more than two pieces, etc).

To compare the influence of the ellipticity of the nanochannels on the cleaving properties, the samples were first laser-processed (across their centreline) with the three beam configurations as shown in Fig. 2(a): Elliptical Bessel Beam (EBB) with the main lobe major axis parallel to the translation direction, y -axis, referred to as EBB-parallel (EBB-p); elliptical Bessel beam with the main lobe major axis orthogonal to the scanning direction (x -axis) which we will refer to as EBB-orthogonal (EBB-o); and circularly Symmetric Bessel Beam (SBB).

FIG. 3. Values of the deflection needed to fracture the samples under 3 point bending test as a function of beam shape and pulse energy. Cleaved samples are represented as green disks, broken ones by red stars, average value by black circles. Left: Symmetrical Bessel Beam; center: EBB-orthogonal; right: EBB-parallel.

In Fig. 3, we plot the deflection to fracture as a function of pulse energy (6, 12 and 18 μJ) for the three illumination conditions mentioned above (Fig. 1(a)). For

each illumination condition and pulse energy, 10 samples were processed. Results are shown as green circles if the sample cleaved and as red stars if it broke. For each set of 10 measurements, mean value and standard deviation are shown in black. Figure 3 shows that SBB with 6 μJ pulse energy never led to cleaving, while this was possible 10 out of 10 times for 12 μJ and 18 μJ pulse energies. The lower value of deflection to fracture obtained for the case of 18 μJ pulse energy in comparison to 12 μJ indicates that cleaving requires smaller pressure for the higher pulse energy and the reduced standard deviation features a higher reproducibility.

FIG. 4. Weibull cumulative distribution fits for the cleavability measurements shown in Fig. 3.

The EBB-orthogonal beam illumination only rarely leads to cleaving whatever the pulse energy. This is in accordance with the numerical simulation of the stress distribution presented before: the stress is concentrated at the vertices of the elliptical channels which obviously poorly contributes to guide a fracture in a direction perpendicular to the major axis of the ellipse. In this configuration, the cleaving plane cannot be guided which deteriorates the ability to cleave.

In contrast, the EBB-parallel beam yields 100% cleaving at 12 and 18 μJ , with much lower deflection as those obtained with Symmetrical Bessel beams, as expected from our numerical simulations. In Fig. 4, we plot the measurements of Fig.3 for SBB and EBB-parallel at 12 and 18 μJ as Weibull cumulative distributions of the deflec-

Energy (μJ)	SBB		EBB-parallel	
	12	18	12	18
α (no unit)	9.4	7.7	10.5	7.0
β (mm)	0.31	0.29	0.19	0.17

TABLE I. Weibull parameters corresponding to the fits of experimental data shown in Fig 4.

tion at fracture d : $W(d) = 1 - \exp(-(\frac{d}{\beta})^\alpha)$. This distribution is characterized by two parameters α and β . Parameter β represents the value of deflection at which statistically 63% of the samples break, while α is the shape parameter which is inversely proportional to distribution variance²⁷. Lowest β parameter and highest α are the preferred configuration for application to material separation. These parameters are summarized in Table I. It is clear from Fig.4 that the EBB-parallel illumination, shown in red, provides steeper ($\alpha > 7$) transitions of the distribution with β reduced by half compared to the case of the symmetric Bessel beam, in blue.

SEM observations of the cleaved edge surface produced after EBB-parallel processing show that the cleaving is perfectly guided by the line of ellipses for all samples produced at 12 and 18 μJ , all channels are cleaved through from top to exit sides and all along the 2 mm length of the samples. SEM images of the proof-of-principle results were reported in reference Meyer *et al.*²⁶ and here we can evaluate the impact of the sub-micron precision cleaving on the strength of the separated parts.

For this, a second series of samples was processed so as to define two parallel laser-processed edges to be tested. Each sample was laser-illuminated along two lines at a distance of 12 mm of each other. Then, the samples were fractured under the 3-point bending test with the blade placed perpendicular to these two lines as shown in Fig. 2(d). Obviously in this case, all samples break since there is no weakening line to guide the fracture. We note that the distance between the edges to be tested is an important parameter for the reproducibility of the measurement. We chose a 12 mm distance since we determined that above 8 mm, the standard deviations obtained were significantly below mean values.

For this experiment, we select out only the illumination conditions that led to a high rate of cleaved samples, i.e. the SBB illumination and EBB-parallel, for both energies of 12 and 18 μJ . Figure 5 shows the results of the 3-point bending test as described above (a), and plotted as a Weibull distribution (b). For applications, the best conditions are those producing samples that contain the minimal amount of micro/nano fractures and can undergo high bending without breaking. We observe that the EBB-parallel shown with red lines produces samples that can undergo 30 % higher bending than those produced by SBB illumination whatever the input pulse energy. This demonstrates that the cleaving by the EBB-parallel based on elliptical channels leaves less defects in the cleaved glass.

In conclusion, our results show that elliptical Bessel

FIG. 5. (a) Values of the deflection needed to fracture the samples prepared by cleaving on 2 sides, as a function of beam shape and pulse energy. (b) Weibull cumulative fits of the same experimental data.

beams used to machine elliptical nanochannels with major access parallel to a targeted cleave direction can strongly improve material separation because of an enhanced and more localized stress distribution. After cleaving, we also showed that the edges are stronger in comparison to processing with symmetric Bessel beams. For the same inter-channel spacing (5 μm), high-repetition rate (100's kHz) industrial lasers are expected enable processing speeds exceeding 1 meter per second. We anticipate these results will impact on the field on laser nano-processing of transparent materials and will foster research on the understanding of material properties at nano-scales around the laser-processed nanochannels.

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